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Bosh muharrir:
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:
Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

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MUNDARIJA

Benazir ustozni yod etib	10
Samarqand davlat veterinariya meditsinasi, chorvachilik va biotexnologiyalar universiteti jamoasi	
Qishloq xo'jaligi taraqqiyotining ustuvor yo'nalishlari.....	12
Yunusov Xudaynazar Beknazarovich	
Agroklasterlarda biznes jarayonlari moliyaviy natijalari hisobini takomillashtirish	14
Alikulov Abdimo'min, Koshkaldal Irina	
Assessment of the ESG rating of banks.....	19
Ruziyeva Elvira, Eshmuradov Ulugbek	
Contract Preferences of Smallholders: Evidence From a Study on Potato Production in Uzbekistan	24
Sanaev Golib, Sanaeva Rakhima, Nurullaev Ulmasjon, Nurullaeva Bakhora, Sanaev Anvar	
Taxation Systems in the Agricultural Production Sphere in the Context of Resistance to Shadow Economy	34
Koshkaldal Iryna, Dombrovska Olena, Alikulov Abdimumin	
Factors Influencing Farmers' Cooperation in Irrigation: A Study of Samarkand Province, Uzbekistan	39
Tadjiev Abdusame Abduxamidovich	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida qishloq xo'jaligida kapital qo'yilmalar hisobi hamda hisobotlarini takomillashtirish.....	43
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna, Raxmatov Jonibek Ismoil o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida ichki auditida muhimlik va auditor riski masalalari.....	50
Ibragimov Abdugapur Karimovich, Qo'ldoshev Dilshod Melixurozovich	
Agroklasterlar ichki sotish jarayonida transfert baholarni belgilashni tashkiliy-uslubiy jihatlarini	57
Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
Auditda regression tahlilni qo'llashning xususiyatlari	64
Tajekeev Ziyatdin Kobeysonovich	
Uzumchilik fermer xo'jaliklarida ishlab chiqarish xarajatlari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	67
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich	
Xalqaro standartlar asosida qishloq xo'jaligida aktivlarni tasniflash, ularning hisobi va hisobotini takomillashtirish.....	71
Egamberdiyeva Salima Rayimovna	
The Place of Digitalisation in the Rural Areas Development of Ukraine.....	76
Riasnianska A. M., Kniaz O. V.	
Yalpi ichki va hududiy mahsulotning ko'payishida faol tadbirkorlikning o'rni	79
Salamov Ibroxim, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Nazarova Maryam Sharipovna	
Inflyatsion targetlash rejimining pul-kredit siyosatini amalga oshirishdagi ahamiyati	84
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich	
Asalarichilikning qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyotidagi o'rni va uni rivojlantirish istiqbollari.....	89
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich	
Uzumchilik majmuining tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmi va uning tamoyillari.....	94
Boltayev Nazarbek Narzullayevich	
Mintaqaviy klasterning xususiyatlari.....	98
Urdushev Hamrakul	
Considerations for Bolstering Entrepreneurship in the Evolution of the Domestic Economy	102
Shadiyeva Gulnora Mardiyevna	
Chorvachilik tarmog'ida ishlab chiqarish samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari.....	107
Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, O'roqov Feruz Ibodullayevich	
Oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari yetishtirishning hududiy jihatlarini	112
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Nazarova Maryam Sharipovna	

Yalpi ichki mahsulot va uni hisoblashni takomillashtirish yo'llari.....	117
Xalmurzaev Mansur, Abdushukurov Xondamir	
Qishloq xo'jaligi korxonalarida tovar-moddiy qiymatliklar hisobini takomillashtirish yo'nalishlari.....	122
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna	
Mamlakatimiz agrar tarmog'ida innovatsiyalarga asoslangan tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirish.....	127
Olimova Nodira hamrakulovna	
Banklarda ichki auditni xalqaro audit standartlari asosida takomillashtirish.....	131
Rizayev Nurbek Qodirovich, Boymatova Chinora Ilxomovna	
Agroklastarlarda asosiy vositalarni modernizatsiyalash va ta'mirlash xarajatlari hisobini takomillashtirish.....	137
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Ibodullaev D., Abdushukurov Xondamir Botiraliyevich	
Davlat budjetida boshqaruv xarajatlarini moliyalashtirishni takomillashtirish yo'llari va xarajatlarning optimallashtiruv muammolari.....	142
Narziyeva Guzal Baxtiyorovna	
Bandlikni ta'minlash va kambag'allikni qisqartirishni yuzaga keltiruvchi sabablar hamda ularning yechimi.....	146
Ahmatova Qunduzbonu Asliddinovna, Sunnatullayev Musurmon Sunnatullo o'g'li, Salamov Ibroxim	
Global iqtisodiy rivojlanish sharoitida yashil iqtisodiyot muammolari.....	151
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Musurmonov Nodirbek Ahmadovich	
Menejer boshqaruvida boshqaruv mehnati va guruhlar dinamikasi.....	155
Xasanova Sitara Islamovna	
G'allachilik klasterlarida buxgalteriya hisobi shakllarini takomillashtirish.....	158
Yuldashev Sherali Xaitovich	
Современность услуг агропромышленного комплекса в условиях инновационной экономики положение дел.....	163
Тураев Баходир Хатамович, Рузиев Хамрокул Жураевич	
Влияние внешних факторов на эффективность производства животноводства.....	170
Хамдамова Насиба Аблакуловна	
Banklarda ichki auditni rejalashtirish masalalari.....	173
Ibragimova Iroda Rashid qizi, Safarov Abdumajit Abdixamidovich	
The Importance of Digital Technologies in the Development of Agriculture.....	179
Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloevich	
Yakka tartibdagi tadbirkorlarni soliqqa tortish o'zini o'zi band qilishni davlat tomonidan tartibga solish shakli sifatida.....	182
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna, Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich	
O'zbekiston pensiya tizimida pensiya hisoblash va to'lashni rivojlantirishda xorijiy mamlakatlar tajribasini uyg'unlashtirish.....	186
Xasanov Baxodir Akramovich, Nurmanov Din-Axmed Tileubayevich	
Uzumchilik mahsulotlari eksportini oshirish omillari.....	193
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich	
Korxonalarining xo'jalik faoliyati hisobining mohiyati, ahamiyati va hisob turlari.....	196
Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich, Tilabov Shohruh Baxriddin o'g'li, Irisboyev Raxmatilla Shavkat o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'zbekistondagi holati va uning rivojlanish istiqbollari.....	200
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Abdullayev Sanjar Sayfiddin o'g'li, Sunnatullayev Musurmon Sunnatulla o'g'li	
Fermer xo'jaliklar faoliyatida investitsiyalarning o'rni.....	204
Nomozova Mahliyo Mampirjon qizi, Yuldashev Muhammad Utkir o'g'li, Solijonova Diyora Xaydarali qizi, Saydullayev Akbarali Akram o'g'li, Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning o'rni va joriy etishdagi imkoniyatlari.....	209
Salamov Ibroxim, Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Ummatov Begzod Ikrom ugli, Bekpolatov Sul-tonxon Sherzod ugli	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida asosiy vositalarni hisobga olishni takomillashtirish.....	214
Xatamov Kobil Xayrievich, Sodiqov Xayrulla Sattorovich	
Improving Cost Accounting for Sales of Agricultural Products in Farms.....	218
Abdimumin Alikulov, Ulugbek Eshmuradov, Khondamir Abdushukurov	

Servis korxonalarini raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tkazishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirish	224
Kurbanova Raxima Jamshedovna	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotning bugungi kundagi holati.....	228
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Eshimova Gulandom Botir qizi, Daniyarov Xurshid Baxtiyarovich	
Qoramolchilikda ozuqa ta'minotini yaxshilash yo'llari	233
Nurullayev Ulug'bek Uytalovich, Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Meva-sabzavotchilik klasterlarida faol tadbirkorlikning iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishdagi o'rni	236
Ibroxim Salomov, Roziyeva Gulxayo Chorievna	
Qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirishning o'ziga xos xususiyatlari.....	242
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Isaxonov Shaxzodjon Nurali o'g'li	
O'zbekiston chorvachiligidagi muammolar va ularning yechimi.....	246
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna, Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Esirgapov Diyor Akramovich, Ulmasov Tohir Suvonqulovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyotini rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning o'rni va ahamiyati	249
Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna, Ulmasov Amirxon Rasul o'g'li, Botirov Bekzod Ulug'bek o'g'li	
Механизмы и инструменты финансирования малых и средних сельскохозяйственных предприятий (На примере Центральноазиатского региона).....	253
Худойбердиева Асила	
Agroklasterlarda kapital qo'yilmalar hisobini xalqaro standartlar asosida takomillashtirish masalalari.....	259
Irisboev Rahmatillo Shavkat o'g'li, Jo'rayeva Diyora Olimjonovna, Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
Milliy iqtisodiyotda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rolini oshirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari	265
Saidxonov Akmalxon	
Improving Accounting and Auditing of Inventories in Agricultural Clusters	269
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasining rivojlanish tendensiyalari va kambag'allikni qisqartirishdagi o'rni.....	272
Rajabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich	
Chorvachilik tarmog'ida mahsulotlarni qayta ishlash samaradorligini oshirish imkoniytlari	277
Salomov Ibroxim, Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Hotamov Adhamjon Asqarjon o'g'li	
Порядок применения и актуальность международных стандартов финансовой отчетности в деятельности коммерческих банков и предприятий	282
Нарзиева Гузал Бахтиёровна, Хомидов Асилбек Отабек угли, Асомиддинов Хусан Асомиддин угли, Болтабаев Диёрбек Омандурди угли	
Savdo korxonalarida segmentar hisobning o'rni va ahamiyati	286
Mardonov Mamed Shavkatovich, Bobomuradova Sarvinoz Ziyadullayevna	
Livestock Development Problems and Prospects in Uzbekistan	289
Khamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Ulmasova Oygul Bakhtiyarovna, Xudayberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
Понятие и учет капитальных вложений в агрокластерах.....	292
Жураева Диёра Олимджановна	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarini innovatsion modernizatsiyalashda iqtisodiy samaradorlikni hisoblash metodini takomillashtirish	297
Kurbanova Raxima Jamshedovna, Umurzoqova Sevinch Karim qizi	
Tarmoq mahsulotlarini ishlab chiqarish va sotishda innovatsion texnologiyalarni qo'llashning iqtisodiy samaradorligi	301
Nazarova Maryam Sharipovna, Kazakova Zulayho Salaxiddinovna	
Maishiy xizmatlar sohasini tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlarini takomillashtirishda raqamli innovatsion texnologiyalarning roli va ahamiyati	304
Quliyev Begimqul Melikovich	
O'zbekiston iqtisodiyotining rivojlanishi va iqtisodiy o'sish uchun barqaror investitsiya muhitini ta'minlash masalalari.....	308
Raximova Umida Rabbimovna, Elmurodova Dilnoza Farxodovna	

Biznesni qo'llab-quvvatlashda iqtisodiy-ijtimoiy holatni yaxshilash imkoniyatlari	311
Salamov Ibroxim, Janibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich, Ulmasova Oygul Baxtiyorovna, Xudayberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
G'alla urug'chiligida boshlang'ich hisob va ichki nazoratni takomillashtirish	315
Yuldashev Sherali Xaitovich, Yusupov Uchqun, Zokirov Behruz	
Baliqchilik xo'jaliklarini rejalashtirishning ahamiyati va bosqichlari.....	318
Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna	
"Yashil" iqtisodiyot: konsepsiyaning shakllanishi va asosiy kategoriyalari.....	321
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Toshpulatova Kamola Xurshed qizi	
Sutchilik yo'nalishidagi xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar faoliyatida marketing elementlaridan foydalanish	324
Urazov Jamshidjon Sa'dullayevich	
Biznes jarayonlarida "xarajat" va "tannarx" kategoriyalarining nazariy jihatlari.....	328
Xondamir Abdushukurov, Ulug'bek Eshmuradov	
Перспективы развития бухгалтерского учета и аудита на основе международных стандартов.....	333
Рахимова Умида Раббимовна, Асомиддинов Хусан Асомиддин угли, Болтабаев Диёрбек Омондурди угли, Хомидов Аслбек Отабек угли	
Asosiy vositalarni hisobga olishning xalqaro va milliy standartlarda aks ettirishning farqli jihatlari	336
Xatamov Kobil Xayrievich, Turabaeva Ozoda Ilxambekovna	
Qishloq hududlarida ekoturizm maskanlarining turistik salohiyati va sig'imi tahlili.....	340
Abduraxmanova Aqida Fayzulla qizi, Xoshimova Sevara Bahromovna, Sayfullaev Umidulla Fazliddin o'g'li	
Chorvachilik tarmoqlarida o'tchilik infratuzilmasining hozirgi holati va istiqboldagi iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari	346
Salamov Ibroxim, Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Tursunov Alpomish Amanovich, Yo'ldoshev Raxim Nuriddin o'g'li	
Qishloq xo'jaligi klasterlari va fermer xo'jaliklari faoliyatida raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish imkoniyatlari	351
Nasimjon Babayev, Dilorom Yorbekova, Umidullo Fayzullayev	
Agroklasterlarda biznes jarayonlari sotish hisobini takomillashtirish	354
Abdunazarova Sevinch, Aliqulova Zebuniso, Eshmuradov Ulug'bek Tashmuratovich	
Iqtisodiyotni modernizatsiyalash sharoitida qishloq xo'jalik ishlab chiqarishining samaradorligi	360
Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Abduxaliqova Farangiz Abduxoliq qizi	
Increasing Efficiency of Catering Enterprises Through Modernization.....	365
Kurbanova Rakhima Jamshedovna	
Chorvachilik majmuasi infratuzilmasi va uni rivojlantirish	369
Nurmanov Sherzod Xujayarovich, Aslonov Xotamjon Sharibboy o'g'li	
Davlat-xususiy sherikchiligini rivojlantirishda klasterlarning ahamiyati	373
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Raxmatullayev Sherzod Mexriddinovich	
Studying the Features of Innovative Development in The Agricultural Sector of the Economy	377
Yorbekova Dilorom Muxammadkulovna	
Chorvachilikda klasterlashning ayrim masalalari	380
Urdushev Hamrakul, Mavlyanov Majid Tuychiyevich	
Issues of Development of "Green Economy" in the Context of the Actualization of the Problem of Ecology and Climate Change.....	385
Mukhayyo Dustova	
Xizmatlar sohasi rivojlanishining aholi turmush darajasiga ta'siri.....	390
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna	
Baliqchilik xo'jaliklarini rivojlantirish prognozini ishlab chiqish masalalari	393
Dosmuratova Shaxista Kengashovna	
Mahalliy soliqlar va mahalliy yig'imlarning iqtisodiy mohiyati.....	396
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Asomiddinov Husan Asomiddin o'g'li	
Turizm korxonalarini hisob siyosatini shakllantirish	400
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich	

Korxonalarda moliyaviy holatini ifodalovchi ko'rsatkichlar tahlili	404
Ishturdiyev Hasan Abdigapparovich, Tilabov Shohruh Baxriddin o'g'li, Yusupova Ergashoy	
Innovatsiya, innovatsion iqtisodiyot atamalarining mohiyati va ulardan samarali foydalanish yo'llari.....	408
Xudoyberdiyeva Marifat Umarovna, Boyjigitov Kamronmirzo Sobirjon o'g'li, Obloberdiyev Shuxrat Sharof o'g'li	
The Processing Indicators of Livestock Products on the Basis of Economic Statistical Models.....	411
Yorbekova Dilorom Muxammadkulovna, Hotamov Adhamjon Asqarjon o'g'li	
Paxta-to'qimachilik klasterlarida tola ishlab chiqarish xarajatlarini tahlili	414
Alikulov Abdimo'min Ismatovich, Farangiz Rustamova	
Meva-sabzavotchilikni rivojlantirishda klaster yondashuvining afzalliklari	419
Eshankulov Sirojiddin Xakimovich	
Prospects for Leaving the Population Out of Poverty	424
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Radjabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich, Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Fayzullayev Umidullo Xayrullo o'g'li	
Tijorat banklarida korrupsiyaga qarshi kurashishning kompayens nazorati usullarini takomillashtirish.....	429
Sultanov Abrorbek Umarali o'g'li, Axmedov Shuxrat Xikmatullayevich	
Segmentar va moliyaviy hisobot tuzishda xo'jalik yurituvchi subyektlar mulkini baholashning metodologik muammolari	435
G'olibjon Alikulov	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotga o'tish orqali yashirin iqtisodiyotni jamiyatga ta'sirini kamaytirish	439
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Abdusalomov Farruh G'ayrat o'g'li	
Sustainable Farming Futures: the Economic Need of Climate Change Program in Uzbekistan.....	443
Akhmadjon Nurullaev, Sanayeva Raxima Amirqulovna, Visola Khasanova, Bakhora Nurullaeva, Anvar Sanaev	
Problems and Prospects of Cadastral Valuation of Land Resources in the Republic of Kazakhstan	447
Berdimurat Nazimgul, Bassybekova Zh.B.	
Значение цифровизации в сельском хозяйстве	451
Сыздықова Азиза Оралбайқызы, Сапарова Айнура Алпамысовна	
Xizmatlar sohasi samaradorligini oshirish masalalari	456
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzakovich, Mardanova Mohidil Otabek qizi, Mirzayev Azzamjon Jonuzokovich	
Aholini o'z-o'zini bandlikka jalb qilish orqali ishsizlik darajasini pasaytirish.....	461
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Jo'rayev Sherali Anor o'g'li	
Innovatsiyani joriy qilishning fermer xo'jaliklari daromadlariga ta'siri	465
Eshboyev Diyorbek Yo'ldosh o'g'li, Sinayev Sherali Islom o'g'li, Ismoyilov Azamat Isroyilovich	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlariga muvofiq daromadni tan olish masalalari.....	471
Kozimjonov Abrorbek	
O'zbekistonda kichik biznes va xususiy tadbirkorlikni rivojlantirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning yutuqlari va muammolari.....	475
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi	
Soliq ma'murchiligida raqamli iqtisodiyotning ahamiyati va uning ilmiy-nazariy asoslari tahlili	479
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Holmirzayev Sardor Ravshan o'g'li, Tursinaliyev Abdulaziz Shokirjon o'g'li	
O'zbekistonda davlat xizmatlari ko'rsatish milliy tizimini rivojlanishi: xronologik tahlil.....	484
Hasanov Habibullo	
Chorvachilikning mamlakat iqtisodiyotidagi ahamiyati va uning rivojlanishi	488
Xamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna, Tirkashev Farxod Mahmudovich, Sayfullayev Akbar Xoljigit o'g'li, Erkinov Samandar Maxmudovich	
O'zbekiston chorvachiligiga oid FAO ma'lumotlari haqida	493
Pardayeva Kamola	
Moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlariga muvofiq xaridorlar bilan tuziladigan shartnomalar asosida tushumni hisobga olishning ahamiyati	498
Norbekov Davron	
Paxtachilik klasterlarida ishlab chiqarishga ta'sir etuvchi omillarning tahlili	502
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Abduraxmonov Orifbek Odiljon o'g'li	

Raqamli iqtisodiyotning zamonamizdagi bugungi o'rnini	506
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Zarmaxmatov Nomozjon Baxodir o'g'li	
Improving Cost Audit in Innovation Activities	510
Mustafoev is the son of Akbar Mustafa	
Konsolidatsiyalashgan moliyaviy hisobotni mxs asosida transformatsiya qilish zaruriyati	514
Xolmurodov Otabek	
Klasterlarni tashkil etishning tashkiliy-iqtisodiy mexanizmlari va ularning mamlakat iqtisodiyotida tutgan o'rnini	521
Javmanov Jamshed Abdusamatovich, Homidov Aslbek Otabek o'g'li, Asomiddinov Husan Asomiddin o'g'li, Boltayev Diyorbek Omondurdi o'g'li	
Soliq imtiyozlarini nazariy asoslash va huquqiy tartibga solish	526
Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich	
Sug'urta shartnomalari va sug'urta majburiyatlari hisobini moliyaviy hisobotning xalqaro standartlari asosida takomillashtirish	531
Ochilov Ilyos Keldiyorovich	
Обеспечение привлекательности инвестиции коммерческих банков	537
Назаров Килич Холмурадович, Нафасов Шохрухбек Хошимович	
O'zbekistonda tashqi savdoning rivojlanishi va muammolari	539
Xudayberdiyev U.	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida mehnatga haq to'lashning nazariy jihatdan tashkiliy-iqtisodiy asoslari	542
Rajabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich, Toshmurodova Dilbar Muzaffar qizi	
Human Capital in Education	546
Ibragimov Mansur Mardonovich, Ergashev Olloyor	
Qishloq joylarida xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini rivojlantirish hamda o'zini o'zi band qilish orqali ishsizlikni kamaytirishning nazariy asoslari	551
Jo'rayev Sherali Anor o'g'li, Abdikarimov Nazirbek Odil o'g'li, Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich	
Uchqora uzumi-mayizini yetishtirishning iqtisodiy samaradorligini oshirish imkoniyatlari	555
Salamov Ibroxim, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, Janibekov Faxriddin Beknazarovich	
Moliyaviy natijalarning tavsifini takomillashtirish	561
Yusupova Farizabonu Zarifovna	
Kambag'allik va uni qisqartirish yo'llari	564
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Do'stiyov Mirabbos Erkin o'g'li	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida aholi turmush darajasini oshirishda xizmat ko'rsatish sohasining ahamiyati	568
Xolmurodov Otabek	
O'zbekistonda aholi turmush darajasi va daromadlarining o'ziga xos xususiyatlari	570
Rajabov Navruzbek Azimjonovich, Uralov Baxtiyor Maxmudovich, Saidmurodov Sardor Mirsalohovich	
SWOT-анализ конкурентоспособности национального туризма в Узбекистане в условиях преодоления последствий пандемии	574
Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi, Abduzoirov Sarvarbek	
Ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy rivojlantirish va aholi turmush darajasini yanada yaxshilashda iqtisodiy samaradorlikni oshirishning ahamiyati	577
Salamov Ibroxim, Kudratov Rizo Turdibayevich, hamdamova Nasiba Ablakulovna	
Jahon iqtisodiyoti va xalqaro savdo munosabatlari	582
Tirkashev Farhod Mahmudovich, Xo'jaqulov Inomjon Rustam o'g'li	
Xizmat ko'rsatish sohasini raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitiga mos rivojlantirishning ayrim masalalari	586
Mirzayev Qulmamat Jonuzakovich, Sherzodova Diyora Sherzod qizi	
Turistik destinatsiyalarni rivojlantirish orqali turistik zonalarni takomillashtirish	589
Raxmonov Siyovush Turob ug'li, Ochilova Mohigul Toshtemir qizi	
Ivermektin, klozantel, iversantapulus dori vositalarining marketing tahlili	592
Raxmadullayev Humoyun Rashid o'g'li, Farmonov Nizom, Salamov Ibroxim	
Цифровая оптимизация для экологической безопасности в агропромышленном комплексе	597
Юнусов Худайназар Бекназарович, Сафарова Лола Улмасовна	

Смысловой – системный анализ процессов обработки плодов и овощей энергии начального импульса.....	602
Курбанов Жамшед Маджидович, Курбонова Мадина Жамшедовна	
Формирования алгоритма расчета эффективности транспортно-логистической системы поставок грузов.....	605
Кубаев Улугбек	
Роль и потенциал севооборота в создании устойчивых и экологически чистых систем в сельском хозяйстве на основе цифровизации	611
Юнусов Худайназар Бекназарович, Сафарова Лола Улмасовна	
Qoramollar uchun ozuqa ratsionini tuzishda innovatsion yondashuv	617
Mavlyanov Majid Tuychiyevich	
Landshaft bog'dorchilikni rivojlantirishda autocad dasturining o'rnini.....	624
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich, Sulaymonov Mirobid Abduxolikovich	
Aniq qishloq xo'jaligida o'zgaruvchan me'yorlarni qo'llash	628
Akbarov Husan O'zbekxonovich, Bekzod Quدراتov	
Raqamli iqtisodiyotda neyron tarmoqlaridan foydalanishning ahamiyati.....	634
Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna	
Iqtisodiy masalalarni tahlil qilish, me'yorlash, rejalashtirish, baholash hamda bashorat qilishda korrelyatsiya va regressiya usuli	637
Aktamova Vasila Uktamovna, Axtamova Umida O'ktam qizi	
Iqtisodiy ekonometrik modelni tuzish hamda avtokorrelyatsiya mavjudligini aniqlash	641
Raximov Abdulaxad Nematovich	
O'zbekistonda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlarini yetishtirishda agrovoltaika texnologiyasini qo'llash istiqbollari	646
Berdiyev G'ayrat Ibragimovich, Eshpulatov Dostonbek Baxodir o'g'li, Malikova Sevinch Telman qizi	
Развитие системы цифровизации в сельском хозяйстве и в народной медицине	650
Рахмонов Фариз Зафаржонович, Мухиддинова Сабрина Мунисовна, Усманова Лайло Рахматуллаевна, Рахмонова Хабиба Нуруллаевна	
Raqamli iqtisodiyot fanlarini o'qitishda zamonaviy pedagogik metodlar va virtual onlayn kurslardan foydalanish.....	653
Sulaymonov Mirobid Abduxolikovich	
Qishloq xo'jaligini boshqarishda raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanishning afzalliklari	656
Ravshanov Sanjar Tolibjonovich	
Ekin maydonlari tuproqlarini tahlil qilish va boshqarishda sun'iy intellekt tizimlaridan foydalanishning o'rnini.....	660
Otoboyeva Aziza Shakirovna, Artikov Farxod Sayfiddinovich, Usanov Yoqub Dilmurod o'g'li	
О некоторых нестандартных способах решения иррациональных уравнений	664
Актамова Васи́ла Уктамовна	
Корхоналарни тугатишнинг норматив ва ташкилий-услугий таъминотини такомиллаштириш	666
Дусмуратов Раджапбай Давлатбаевич	
Юридик шахсларни тугатишнинг норматив-ҳуқуқий таъминоти.....	670
Давлетов Икрам Рахимберганович	
Саноат корхоналарида мулкрий муносабатларни тартибга солишнинг илмий назарий асослари.....	674
Бобобеков Эргаш Абдумаликович	

THE IMPORTANCE OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF AGRICULTURE

Rabbimov Elbek Abdulloyevich

Senior lecturer of the “Accounting and Statistics” department of TSUE
Samarkand branch, PhD

Abstract: This article discusses the role of digital technologies in the development and improvement of agricultural efficiency in the digital economy. The positive aspects of the use of cloud technologies in the development of the industry and the priority directions of digitalization of the agro-industrial complex in the conditions of the digital economy of our republic are shown.

Key words: Agriculture, digital economy, efficiency, cloud technologies, digitalization, virtualization, social network.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida qishloq xo'jaligini rivojlantirish va samaradorligini oshirishda raqamli texnologiyalarning tutgan o'rni, sohani rivojlantirishda “bulutli” texnologiyalardan foydalanishning ijobiy jihatlari va respublikamizda raqamli iqtisodiyot sharoitida qishloq xo'jaligi sohasini raqamlashtirishning ustuvor yo'nalishlari ko'rsatilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: qishloq xo'jaligi, raqamli iqtisodiyot, samaradorlik, “bulutli” texnologiyalar, raqamlashtirish, virtuallashuv, ijtimoiy tarmoq.

Аннотация: В данной статье обсуждается роль цифровых технологий в развитии и повышении эффективности сельского хозяйства в условиях цифровой экономики. Показаны положительные стороны использования “облачных” технологий в развитии отрасли и приоритетные направления цифровизации агропромышленного комплекса в условиях цифровой экономики нашей республики.

Ключевые слова: Сельское хозяйство, цифровая экономика, эффективность, “облачные” технологии, цифровизация, виртуализация, социальная сеть.

INTRODUCTION

Today, digital technologies cover all industries. Agriculture, which is a strategic sector for our country, is no exception. Digital transformation of agriculture requires experts to acquire new knowledge, as well as new “smart” solutions from them. Digitization is considered the main vector of agricultural development, and in recent years, a lot of attention has been paid to the rapid development of the agricultural sector and the attraction of advanced technologies to the sector. Decision No. PQ-257 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 2, 2023 “On measures to introduce advanced digital technologies in the field of agriculture” [1] is the reason for significant changes in the field in recent years is happening.

Every innovation in the mechanization and automation of agricultural production brings the industry to a new stage of development. By introducing advanced information technology (IT) in modern agriculture, it is possible to reduce the amount of manual labor and costs, while increasing productivity and yield.

The use of digital technologies in agriculture is not only the use of computers, but digital technologies allow controlling all stages of plant or animal husbandry. “Smart” devices perform functions such as measuring and transmitting parameters of soil, plants, microclimate, etc. All this information from a special device (sensor), drones and other equipment is analyzed by special programs. Farmers and agronomists will be able to determine the best time to plant or harvest, calculate fertilizer rates, and predict yields using mobile or online applications.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS

Today, about 70 percent of farms in the United States, Canada, and Europe are using smart technologies for agriculture. [2]

According to the United Nations report, by 2030, information and communication technologies (ICT) should provide as many opportunities as possible to increase the efficiency of resource use in Europe and the CIS

countries. Ensuring the social and economic security of the population and the national strategic development of countries is explained by the presence of digital technologies. [3]

At the level of state policy, Kazakhstan has determined the implementation of the following main measures in the development of its agro-industry:

- 1) attracting small and medium-sized farmers to agricultural cooperatives;
- 2) development of export potential of local products;
- 3) creation of conditions for effective use of land resources;
- 4) development of trade and logistics infrastructure;
- 5) Support of agricultural scientific and technical personnel, as well as information provision of agro-industry.
- 6) Development of the state program "E-APK" aimed at the development of agriculture.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Monographic, comparative analysis, expert evaluation, induction-deduction, and scientific abstraction methods of economic analysis were used to reveal the possibilities of agricultural development and efficiency improvement in the conditions of the digital economy in our republic.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

The role of IT in the rapid development of the agricultural sector in the future is incomparable. "Cloud" technologies are of particular importance in the development of agricultural enterprises in the conditions of the digital economy.

According to experts, the term "cloud" is used as a synonym for the term "internet". In other words, the use of "cloud" i.e. "remote server internet-based" system is an important task in finding a global consumer of high-quality goods, products and services in the field of production and non-production.

"Cloud" technologies are considered to have evolutionary progress in recent years. Therefore, the use of "cloud" technologies in the field of agriculture opens up economic opportunities aimed at finding new consumers.

Based on the above, the so-called "cloud" technologies in the field of agriculture are a convenient tool for storing and processing information related to the field, which includes various software, communication channels, and the goals, tasks and technical requirements for their use. will consist of processes that include the implementation of projects.

"Cloud" technologies in the field of agriculture have the following features:

- First, the necessary information, analyzes and conclusions are all stored in the "cloud";
- Secondly, based on these technologies, it is possible to manage programs remotely;
- Thirdly, there is no limit to the amount of data used in the agricultural sector by cloud technologies, often the size of such data is millions of gigabytes;
- Fourthly, in "cloud" technologies, it is possible to use the "cloud" in any operating system, and access to programs in these technologies is carried out through web browsers;
- Fifth, in such technologies, separate basic blocks are distinguished as a technological solution to minimize the participation of the operators of this process;
- Sixth, "cloud" technologies have a mechanism of protection against the loss of important data, in which the necessary data are automatically saved, copies are placed on backup servers, that is, their complete security is ensured.

At the same time, the use of "cloud" computing based on "cloud" technologies is of particular importance in agriculture. "Cloud" computing means a system of providing information on the agricultural sector in the form of Internet services and to their users on the basis of computer resources.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Based on the above, the following are the priority directions of digitization of the agricultural sector in the conditions of the digital economy in our republic:

1. As a result of the use of modern technologies in agriculture, less expenses are incurred and more income is created.
2. As a result of the digitization of the agricultural sector, it is ensured that labor productivity increases sharply and economic efficiency is achieved without attracting excess labor resources.
3. Modern possibilities of using normative-legal documents and other norms and regulations established in the field will be created.
4. Digitization of the agricultural sector creates an opportunity to prevent corruption and (eliminate the hidden economy) in various sectors and sectors of the economy.
5. Economic conditions will be created for attracting innovative technologies to the field and for effective use of the results achieved by developed countries in this field.
6. Digitization of the agricultural sector creates a systematic possibility of obtaining high income and profit based on the involvement of qualified specialists in the field.

References:

1. O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2023-yil 2-avgustdagi "Qishloq xo'jaligi sohasiga ilg'or raqamli texnologiyalarni joriy qilish chora-tadbirlari to'g'risida"gi PQ-257-sonli qarori.
2. Abdulloevich R. E. (2022). Main directions of development of advertising services in the digital economy. *World Economics and Finance Bulletin*, 9, 181–185.
3. Гвоздева, О. В. Применение "умного землепользования" в России и зарубежных странах / О. В. Гвоздева, Ю. С. Сеница, Е. Ю. Колбнева // *Московский экономический журнал*. – 2020. – № 10. – С. 2. – DOI 10.24412/2413-046X-2020–10677.
4. <https://www.tadviser.ru>
5. www.lex.uz

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Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Rus tili muharriri: Abdimo'min Alikulov, i.f.d., professor

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